

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

SMART DEVICES

A TOOLSET OF

ENVIRONMENTAL SENSORS TO

MONITOR THE IEQ

[SMART WEST]

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE 2

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1. SUMMARY

The goal of this report is to describe the process of identifying and selecting a toolset of portable environmental sensors to monitor the Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) of the remote worker environment. The first step was to conduct a literature analysis to identify the most up-to-date portable sensors available. This was followed by a market analysis to verify which of these sensors were available on the Italian market.

Once a list of available sensors had been compiled, a particular set of sensors was identified and installed into a reference office room. This was done in order to verify and calibrate the measurements of the new sensors against those of sensors that had already been acquired by the research group. Additionally, this step allowed the researchers to assess the capabilities of the new sensors in a real-world setting.

Following this step, the sensors may be used remotely on the test cases in order to measure the IEQ during the working time. This data will be used to assess the IEQ of the remote worker environment and to identify any potential areas for improvement.

2. BACKGROUND

Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) is a broad concept that encompasses the thermal, lighting, acoustic, and air quality conditions of indoor spaces. It has a significant impact on the comfort, well-being, health, and productivity of occupants, especially in office settings where people spend most of their time.

Comfort requirements affect considerably the building energy demand, the productivity and workers wellbeing, as also envisioned by the latest recast of EU directive 844/2018 which relates the energy efficiency of buildings to their ability to optimize “health, indoor air quality and comfort levels” while guaranteeing their cost optimality. Considering that the principal purpose of an HVAC system is to provide indoor climate conditions that are adequate for the thermal comfort, therefore driving the transition from optimal design to operation of highly-performing buildings, it is evident that the very own thermal comfort is the driver for space heating and cooling energy demands and there has been a new research interest in how can be measured over long periods of time and with sensor that have a reasonable installation and operation cost.

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in IEQ research, driven in part by the fact that people now spend over 90% of their time indoors. In addition to the general concern about IEQ, over the last decades, in the lighting domain, a more accurate

understanding of the mechanisms through which light entrains human circadian rhythms has been achieved, with the consequence of raising the awareness and the interest about the relationship between people exposure to light and their health and well-being (non-visual effects of light). Light plays a fundamental role in regulating long-term as well as acute physiological and behavioral functions, such as sleep, alertness, cognitive functions etc., but the evaluation of indoor lighting condition in terms of non-visual effects of light requires the definition of new methodological approaches, since quantities to be evaluated, instruments and measurement procedures are different from those usually adopted to assess visual performance and comfort.

As a result, there is a growing demand for methodological approaches to IEQ evaluation that can consider all four domains simultaneously, rather than treating them as independent entities and for portable/remote devices at small cost.

This is now possible thanks to the advent of low-cost wireless sensor networks and cloud software platforms. Low-cost wireless sensor networks and cloud software platforms have made it possible to develop these methods. These technologies allow us to collect and analyze large amounts of data on IEQ conditions in real time, giving us a more complete and accurate understanding of how these conditions affect people.

Some examples can be found in the recent literature. Tiele et al. developed a small, battery-powered device that can measure many different aspects of indoor air quality, including temperature, humidity, light levels, noise levels, and air pollutants. The device takes measurements every 10 minutes and can be used to monitor indoor air quality in work environments. The device was calibrated using a commercial air quality monitor, and the temperature and carbon dioxide readings were adjusted to ensure accuracy. The device was then placed in a sealed chamber with the commercial air quality monitor to determine the baseline characteristics of the device.

Parkinson et al. (2019) developed a low-cost indoor environmental quality (IEQ) monitoring device called SAMBA. SAMBA is designed to be placed on office desks and monitors a variety of parameters, including air temperature, relative humidity, globe temperature, air velocity, sound pressure level, illuminance, total volatile organic compounds, formaldehyde, carbon monoxide, and carbon dioxide. SAMBA consists of two separate units connected by an Ethernet cable. The satellite unit contains all of the temperature-sensitive transducers to prevent other heat-generating components from affecting their measurements.

At Politecnico di Torino, the design, development, and metrological characterization of a low-cost multi-sensor device called PROMET&O (PROactive Monitoring for indoor EnvironmenTal quality & cOmfort) was carried out under the supervision of A. Astolfi et al (2023). PROMET&O measures a variety of indoor environmental quality (IEQ) parameters, including air temperature and relative humidity, illuminance, sound pressure level, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, particulate matter, formaldehyde, and nitrogen dioxide. Particular attention was devoted to identify specific calibration procedures for each measurement quantity, tailored to the requirements of the respective sensor. The percentage of permeable case surface and the sensor allocation on the calibration results was also investigated.

For what concerns the monitoring of people exposure to light, to assess the adequacy of lighting conditions to entrain human biological rhythms, or acute effects such as alertness, cognitive functions etc., the spectral characteristics of light, the intensity of light and the duration of exposure are meaningful aspects to be considered. New instruments and measurement procedures have been developed, based on the use of wearable sensors able to measure relevant quantities of light (light-dosimeters) or to record environmental light conditions together with person's physical activity using devices typically worn on the wrist (actimetry or actigraphy). Some instruments are already commercially available, some have been developed by research centers.

The first light-dosimeters (Daysimeter and Daysimeter-D) were developed at the Lighting Research Center of the Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, Rensselaer NY, USA. (Bierman et al. 2005; Figueiro et. Al.).

In the following years, other wearable devices to record data related to the circadian effects of light were developed in other research centers. Stampfli J.R. et al. (2023) developed the Light-Dosimeter LIDO to investigate the non-visual response to light. The device uses a multichannel sensor to measure the optical radiation in the visible range (380-780 nm), includes an acceleration sensor to track the tilt of the device and a push button to mark events. The device comes with a software package (LIDO Studio), that can be used to program and activate the sensor and to download and initially analyse the data. Dumortier et al. (2023) developed the LIGHTMONITOR (LIMO), a wearable device which measures the spectrum of light to which a person is exposed as well as its day and night activity. In this case the device is equipped with a sensor that provides 75 spectral irradiances in the visual range of the optical radiation, while the activity is provided in terms of tri-axial acceleration and angular rate. The device comes with a

docking station for battery charge and data transfer. The light-dosimeters have been mainly developed to measure the light incident on the persons' eye and to provide data or quantities related to the non-visual effects of light (quantity and spectral characteristics of the incident optical radiation over time). Other devices, less accurate in recording the spectral characteristics of light or the quantity of light actually incident on the person eye have been developed, with a more specific focus on the relationship between light and long-term health effects. In Danilenco et al. the results of a market analysis of actimeters, able to record both light conditions and motion activity, is reported. Seventeen light-and-motion recorders were analysed and compared. They were reviewed for appearance, dimensions, weight, mounting, battery, sensors, features, communication interface, and software. The results of the analyse demonstrated that all devices differed from each other in several features. In particular, only six devices are equipped with a light sensor that can account, at least in simplified way (blue light), of the spectral characteristics of the incident light.

3. OFF-THE-SHELF PRODUCTS ON THE MARKET

Recently, there have been a number of small and portable devices available to monitor and measure indoor environmental quality (IEQ). These devices typically measure parameters related to the air quality and thermal comfort, such as air temperature, relative humidity, particulate matter, carbon dioxide, volatile organic compounds and less frequently they also measure sound levels and illuminance.

Commercially, some small and portable IEQ monitoring devices are the following:

- Aeroqual Series 300 Portable Indoor Air Quality Monitor (<https://www.aeroqual.com/products/s-series-portable-air-monitors/series-300-portable-indoor-monitor>)
- Airthings Wave Plus (<https://www.airthings.com/it/wave-plus>)
- Aranet4 (<https://aranet.com/products/aranet4/>)
- Foobot Air Monitor (<https://foobot.io/guides/smart-indoor-air-quality-monitor.php>)
- Netatmo Smart Indoor Air Quality Monitor (<https://www.netatmo.com/it-it/smart-indoor-air-quality-monitor>)
- Temtop P25B (<https://temtopus.com/>)
- AirCare (<https://www.aircare.it/>)

Most of them are designed to monitor the indoor air quality and then have enlarged their capabilities to other aspects of IEQ. Some devices also have mobile apps that allow you to view the data remotely, however, the analyses that can be done are limited to report or do not allow to determine indexes or relate the data with the feedback from the occupants.

In the following bullet list, the main features of each commercial tool are summarized.

- **Aeroqual Series 300 Portable Indoor Air Quality Monitor**
(<https://www.aeroqual.com/products/s-series-portable-air-monitors/series-300-portable-indoor-monitor>)

It can measure a wide range of indoor air quality parameters, including:

- Air Temperature
- Air Relative Humidity
- Carbon dioxide
- Carbon monoxide
- Volatile organic compounds (VOCs)
- Particulate matter (PM2.5 and PM10)
- Ozone (O3)
- Nitrogen dioxide (NO2)g
- Sulfur dioxide (SO2)
- Hydrogen sulfide (H2S)

Moreover, some interchangeable sensor heads allow for easy customization to meet specific monitoring needs. It can be used in a variety of settings, including homes, offices, schools, and industrial facilities. A Liquid Cristal display provides clear and easy-to-read data. Audible and visual alarms can be set to alert users to hazardous conditions. Data logging capabilities allow for long-term monitoring and trend analysis. Power supply through rechargeable battery up to 8 hours of continuous operation. Rugged construction is designed to withstand harsh environments.

- **Airthings Wave Plus** (<https://www.airthings.com/it/wave-plus>)

It measures a variety of indoor air quality parameters, including:

- Air Temperature
- Air relative Humidity
- Carbon dioxide (CO₂)
- Air pressure
- Total volatile organic compounds (TVOCs)
- Radon

The power supply is provided through batteries (up to 2 years on a single set of batteries). Bluetooth connectivity allows for easy data transfer to a smartphone or tablet. Airthings Wave app provides real-time data and insights into indoor air quality. Visual indicator (red/yellow/green glow ring) provides at-a-glance feedback on air quality.

The Airthings Wave Plus is a comprehensive and easy-to-use indoor air quality monitor. It is ideal for use in homes, offices, schools, and other indoor environments.

- **Aranet4** (<https://aranet.com/products/aranet4/>)

It measures a variety of indoor air quality parameters, including:

- Air Temperature
- Air relative Humidity
- Carbon dioxide (CO₂)
- Atmospheric pressure

The measure of CO₂ levels is done through a non-dispersive infrared (NDIR) sensor. A periodical calibration is recommended every 6-12 months. The power supply is provided through batteries (up to 2 years on a single set of batteries). Bluetooth connectivity allows for easy data transfer to a smartphone or tablet. Aranet4 app provides real-time data and insights into indoor air quality and track CO₂ levels over time. Visual indicator (green/yellow/red LED) provides at-a-glance feedback on air quality. The Aranet4 can be used in homes, offices, schools, and other indoor environments.

- **Foobot Air Monitor** (<https://foobot.io/guides/smart-indoor-air-quality-monitor.php>)

It measures a variety of indoor air quality parameters, including:

- Air Temperature
- Air Relative Humidity
- Carbon dioxide (CO₂)
- Carbon monoxide (CO)
- Particulate matter (PM2.5 and PM10)
- TVOCs

The measure of PM2.5 and PM10 levels is done through a laser scattering sensor. The measure of TVOC levels is done through a metal oxide semiconductor (MOS) sensor. The measure of CO₂ levels is done through a non-dispersive infrared (NDIR). A periodical calibration is recommended every 6-12 months. Color-coded LED ring provides at-a-glance feedback on air quality. The device supports IFTTT and Amazon Alexa for smart home integration. The Foobot Air Monitor can be used in homes, offices, schools, and other indoor environments.

- **Netatmo Smart Indoor Air Quality Monitor** (<https://www.netatmo.com/it-it/smart-indoor-air-quality-monitor>)

It measures and tracks over time a variety of indoor air quality parameters, including:

- Air Temperature
- Air Relative Humidity
- Carbon dioxide (CO₂)
- Noise level

The measure of CO₂ levels is done through a non-dispersive infrared (NDIR) sensor. The measure of relative humidity levels is done through a capacitive sensor. The measure of noise levels is done through a MEMS (Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems) microphone. Personalized recommendations for improving indoor air quality are provided by the tool. The device can be connected to other Netatmo devices for a complete home monitoring solution, to be used in homes, offices, and other indoor environments.

- **Temtop P25B** (<https://temtopus.com/>)

It measures a variety of indoor air quality parameters, including:

- Air Temperature
- Air Relative Humidity
- Particulate matter (PM2.5 and PM10)
- Carbon dioxide (CO₂)

The measure of PM2.5 and PM10 levels is done through a laser scattering sensor. The measure of CO₂ levels is done through a non-dispersive infrared (NDIR). Power supply through rechargeable battery up to 8 hours of continuous operation. A large LCD display provides clear and easy-to-read data. Audible and visual alarms can be set to alert users to hazardous conditions. It has also data logging capabilities allowing for long-term monitoring and trend analyses.

- **AirCare** (<https://www.aircare.it/>)

It measures a variety of indoor air quality parameters, including:

- Air Temperature
- Air Relative Humidity
- Atmospheric pressure
- Particulate matter (PM2.5 and PM10)
- Carbon dioxide (CO₂)
- Volatile organic compounds (VOCs)
- Sound pressure level
- Illuminance
- Electromog from WIFI, LF and HF

The measure of PM2.5 and PM10 levels is done through a laser scattering sensor. The measure of CO₂ levels is done through a NDIR. The measure of TVOC levels is done through a MOS sensor. In 2022 Aircare was officially certified according to the European norm UNI CEI EN ISO/IEC 17025:2018 covering the measurement of PM2.5, CO₂ and TVOC. A periodical calibration is recommended every 6-12 months. Power is supplied through a USB cable. Data is transmitted to a cloud platform for real-time monitoring and analysis. Users can access their data through the AirCare app or web portal. The app

provides personalized recommendations for improving indoor air quality. The AirCare device can be integrated with other smart home devices.

As regards the PROM&TEO multi-sensor, even though the characteristics are quite in line with the scope of the SMARTWEST project, it was verified that it was not possible to buy some of them with the NODES projects funds from another Department of the same beneficiary institution. Given this picture, even though the characteristics of the multi-sensor were quite interesting (a further step from the AirCare) and the device was considered in the scientific review and in the market analysis, it was not possible to be supplied.

The multi sensors developed for IEQ monitoring are sometimes equipped with sensors for measuring photopic illuminance (e.g. Aircare and Prometeo) but never for monitoring people exposure to light in terms of melanomic/circadian quantities. A analysis of products on the market, focused on wearable light dosimeters was carried out.

Commercially, some wearable light-dosimeters are the following:

- **Nanolambda Spectroradiometer** (https://nanolambda.myshopify.com/products/xl-500-ble-spectroradiometer?_pos=1&_sid=3ccd12e56&_ss=r)

The NanoLambda Spectroradiometer is a compact and lightweight spectroradiometer that can be used to measure the spectral power distribution (SPD) of light. It can be used as a portable device or as a spectrum recorder with free Android/iOS App, internal memory and long lasting rechargeable battery. It has a wavelength range of 390-1000nm and a spectral resolution of 10-40nm. The spectroradiometer is also equipped with a Bluetooth interface for easy connection to smartphones and tablets. Its key features are:

- Wide wavelength range (390-1000nm)
- High spectral resolution (10-40nm)
- Bluetooth interface for easy connection to smartphones and tablets
- Measures SPD, Photopic illuminance, CIE S026 a-opic Illuminances, X, Y, Z, CIE xy, CIE uv, CCT, CRI, and more
- Individually calibrated for device-to-device repeatability
- Memory for over 8,000 measurements
- Ultra low power consumption and use of rechargeable battery

– **Condor Instrument ActiLumus**

The Condor Instrument ActiLumus is a portable and versatile light sensor capable of estimating Melanopic EDI and Photopic Lux through the combination of 10 different channels of light

It has a wide wavelength range of 380-1000nm and a spectral resolution of 10nm. Its key features are:

- Wide wavelength range (380-1000nm)
- Built-in cosine corrector for accurate measurements of diffuse light
- Data logging function for storing and transferring data to a computer
- Variety of measurement modes (continuous, average, peak)
- NIST traceable calibration

– **LYS button**

The LYS Button is a wearable light sensor that can be used to track light exposure and movement. The sensor is comprised of a tristimulus filter that captures light in three wavebands (RGB), plus one channel with sensitivity in the near IR. It is a small and lightweight device that can be clipped to clothing or worn on a wristband. The LYS Button is also water and dust resistant, making it suitable for everyday use. Its main features are:

- Up to 5 days battery life on a single charge
- 15 seconds sampling rate
- Tracks light exposure and movement
- Measures: photopic illuminance, melanopic EDI (m-EDI), correlated color temperature (CCT)
- Can be used to track circadian rhythms
- Can be used to assess indoor environmental quality
- Can be used to research the effects of light on human health and performance

In order to select one or a combination of devices, the trade-off between the following factors was taken into account:

Cost: The sensors and tools needed to be affordable, both in terms of the initial purchase price and the ongoing cost of operation and maintenance.

Ease of use: The sensors and tools needed to be easy to install and use, even for people with no prior experience in environmental monitoring.

Accuracy: The sensors and tools needed to provide accurate and reliable data.

Data collection, storage, and analysis: The sensors and tools needed to be able to collect, store, and analyze data in a way that was easy to understand and use, without the necessity to go to the remote worker environment.

Considering those factors, it was selected the AirCare device, whose approximate cost is around 1,100 € (cost for the device and for two-years cloud service) and a first set of three devices was purchased. Attached you can find the design specifications of the device.

4. THE DEVICE AND ITS VALIDATION

While waiting for the delivery of the three indoor environmental monitoring devices that were purchased with NODES project funds, we were able to obtain one device more quickly that was purchased with other funds. We used this device to conduct installation set-ups and data reading tests in the TEBE L2AB experimental laboratory. In the laboratory, we compared the measurements from the device to the measurements from other instruments with varying degrees of theoretical accuracy.

The AirCare sensor (on the desk) in the TEBE L2AB at Politecnico di Torino – Department of Energy, next to other sensors (a thermal comfort station from TESTO, a NET radiometer, a wired DAQ (Data Acquisition), a Raspberry low cost DAQ and other free-standing sensors) installed in a worker position

This additional device allowed us to start our research and development work earlier than we would have been able to otherwise in fields. It also gave us the opportunity to test and refine our data collection and analysis procedures before we received the three devices that were purchased with NODES project funds. This comparison will also help to assess the accuracy of the new device and to identify any areas where improvement

was needed as can be seen in the graph below that compares the illuminance trends from the AirCare sensor and the Gigahertzing sensor.

Comparison between two trends measurements of desk illuminance (orange: Gigahertzing sensor; blue: AirCare sensor)

Overall, the ability to obtain one device early on was a valuable asset. It allowed us to start our research and development work earlier, and it gave us the opportunity to test and refine our data collection and analysis procedures.

First analyses showed that the outcome from thermal and indoor air quality are reliable and complete, while the lighting analyses are quite simplified and other lighting measurements may be added to the assess the quality and the non-visual effects of light on the performance of workers.

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